

SHOPPERS PERCEPTION TOWARDS MALL RETAIL FORMATS IN CHENNAI CITY

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Abstract:

Shopping mall is a collection of stores housed under one roof. To attract Shoppers, forum mall have been altering and updating their styles frequently. There are many elements that can influence customer's decision on where to shop. The current research is on the focus of Chennai environment. The goal of this study is to determine the characteristics that influence Shoppers perception towards choosing a mall. A mall intercept study was done to investigate the characteristics that impact mall selection. Sample included 50 active mall shoppers. Totally four factors which influence the selection of shopping malls from consumer's view point were identified with a structure of questionnaire. This research would aid mall owners and retail marketers in gaining a better understanding of buyer's perspectives on why they choose a mall and to look at the functioning of shopping malls in Shoppers perspective by looking into the elements that influence shopping mall visits and demonstrating how these aspects differ depending on Shoppers shopping habits and shopping mall kinds. They can plan their mall strategy using these as a foundation. The purpose of this research is to determine the Shoppers perception at forum mall.

Keywords: Sustainable, Services, Strategies, Shoppers, Shopping, Consumer, Mall, Shopping Experience.

Introduction:

Shopping is an essential aspect of life .People's lifestyles have changed and they wanted to shop at a location where they can get everything they need under one roof. As a result of India's economic prosperity and shift in consumer culture, shopping malls have exploded in popularity, displacing conventional department stores and retail outlets. It has a variety of stores, restaurants and entertainment options. This research goal was to determine the impact of shopping mall services on consumer perception. Only primary data is used in this research. Shopping malls format attract shoppers and sellers as well as Shoppers by providing sufficient time for variety and an enjoyable shopping experience. However due to hectic competition between malls Management have began to investigate different techniques for sizing client enjoyment. Shoppers flock to shopping malls because of the variety of products, sales incentives, store collections, economic rewards and gains. In emerging nations, shopping methods and the growth have been key trends in retailing. Shopping malls are taking over traditional bazaars in our economic and social lives. Shopping malls are not only the place for shopping rather it's a great place to relax and have fun with entertainment. Shoppers spend a significant amount of time in shopping malls because they have a large number of stores and

activities that grab Shoppers attention and provide numerous benefits to them. Similar researches have been conducted by many authors (Benita, 2021; Monica, 2021; Kumar, 2020; Kumar & Shree, 2019; Monica & Supriya, 2019; Mahesh & Uma Rani, 2019; Mahesh, Gigi, & Uma Rani, 2019; Robert & Monisha, 2019; Kumar & Shree, 2018).

The Forum Vijaya Mall, established by the Prestige Group in Vadapalani, Chennai on 2013. This mall includes over 650000 square feet of retail space. Its four stories house almost 100 stories. Brands like Spar Hypermarket, Max, Marks & Spencer, Westside, Lifestyle, Rmkv, and Fab India are some of the Chennai-based companies which attracts the shoppers. Huge footfall in forum mall is dependent on 9 screens of SPI cinema's palazzo multiplex and an IMAX screen.

Review of Literature:

1) **Dr. Archana and DhimanKuvad (2017)** - Gujarat city was the location for this research. In the recent decade, India's retail sector has grown rapidly and foreign investment, the state of the global economy, and new economic policies are all factors that have contributed to the development of modern retail. In tier I and tier II cities, shopping malls are also rapidly expanding. Consumer behavior in a shopping mall is the subject of this study. The study's main goal is to learn about the purchasing habits of people who visit shopping malls, as well as gender differences in shopping mall format behavior. This is a quantitative study, and the primary data will be obtained via a questionnaire. The sample size will be 50 men and 50 women. The findings of this study show that people in Gujarat enjoy shopping, that the majority of respondents are unaware of safety measures at shopping malls, and that men and women have similar purchasing habits. The Gender Men agree that they go to the mall for amusement, while women go to the mall primarily to shop and occasionally for fun. The purpose of this study is to look at the purchase habits of shopping mall Shoppers' in Bhavnagar, Gujarat. Small, unorganised enterprises, such as khirana stores, dominate the market. Shopping at malls has become a popular time pass.

2) **Asha (2017)** - Chennai was the site of this study. Shopping malls are often seen as a symbol of modern living. "One-stop shopping" makes people feel more at ease. This research primarily focuses on visitor purchasing behaviour and how demographical factors impact consumer purchasing behaviour, as well as determining customer preferences in shopping malls. The Demographic factors play a significant effect on customer purchasing behaviour in shopping malls, according to the findings. The majority of shoppers like shopping malls because of collective entertainment, and a diverse selection of high-quality goods. For clothes, shoes, and food, the majority of individuals favour shopping malls.

3) **Pooja Khanna, Suresh Seth (2018)** - According to the research, India's retail mall formats are undergoing momentous changes. The principle of this study was to examine the factors that are influencing the Shoppers purchasing in mall formats in a tier-II city. The regression study also demonstrated that Enjoyment, Promotional Offers, Hedonic dimensions, Stress Relieving, and exhilaration are all important factors.

4) **Cynthia Astono (2014)** - ABC Mall and XYZ Mall are two retail malls that are in the midst of a fierce fight. Despite the fact that ABC Mall is Surabaya's newest shopping mall, XYZ Mall, which has been there for a while, is continuously growing sector. The study's goal was to determine which characteristics of shopping malls are capable of increasing consumer happiness.

5) **Rajkumar R. Rathod, Ph.D. (2017)**-People are starting to switch from unorganised to organised retail. Many people prefer shopping in shopping malls because they provide a one-stop shop, many branded products under one roof, and entertainment. The main goal of this research was to learn about customer attitudes toward mall culture and what factors influence visitors' attitudes toward mall culture. This was an empirical study with a sample size of 250 people. Visit a shopping centre and collect primary data using a structured questionnaire and basic random sampling procedures. And the researcher employs a 5-point Likert scale. The findings of this survey show that Indians have gradually assimilated or acclimated to mall culture; most tourists enjoy shopping malls because of the variety of brands, interesting activities, children's zone, and ideal place to hang out with friends and families. The retail mall is under threat from online purchasing.

6) **SandeepBhanot(2017)**- The study attempts that using a sample of 770 mall consumers from Mumbai and Navi Mumbai, the researcher investigates mall-shopping patterns in India and attempts to discover and contrast possible gender differences. When it planning to visit a mall and spending money there, there is no significant difference between male and female Shoppers.

7) **AadilWani (2017)** - The primary goal of this study, according to the researcher, was to look at the buying habits of young people in shopping malls, such as how often they go, how much time they spend there, and how much money they spend there. This assists merchants in analysing present and future Shoppers, consequently guiding shop design and marketing communications strategy.

Research Methodology:

This study is both descriptive and analytical comprising only the primary data. Primary data with a sample of 50 shoppers has been collected from different Shoppers on a single day through the questionnaire method and the samples are chosen by Convenience sampling method. Questionnaire has been used as the research instrument. The data's collected from the questionnaire were analysed and interpreted using SPSS.

Research Design:

This study was based on the perception on Shoppers in forum mall on collected samples from Chennai city. Descriptive research contains data in order to answer the research questions about the research's current state.

Primary Data:

Primary data is collected through well-formed questionnaire with direct Shoppers in the mall. This questionnaire contains quantitative and qualitative multiple choice questions and the respondents are asked to choose the best choice among the given multiple choices.

Sample size:

Questionnaire is used to collect data from 50 people in the forum mall.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage Analysis distribution of the demographic variables:

S. No	Demographic Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Gender	Male	29	58
		Female	21	42
2	Age	Below 20	3	6
		20-30	35	70
		30-45	8	16
		Above 45	4	8
3	Occupation	Student	19	38
		Housewife	2	4
		Business person	6	12
		Working Professional	23	46
4	Education	School	4	8
		Bachelor Degree	27	54
		Master Degree	19	38
		Uneducated	0	0

Interpretation:

From the above table, it is inferred that 58 percent of respondents are male and 42 percent of respondents are female.

From the above table, it is inferred that more than 74.5% of the respondents are from the age group of 18 – 25.

From the above analysis, the majority of data is completed from under graduate students with the percentage of 61.8%

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Table 2- Mean Analysis:

Analysis of mean based on the atmosphere of forum mall.

S. No	Dimensions of Atmosphere	Mean	Rank
1	I like the atmosphere in this mall (Atmosphere)	4.6000	1
2	This mall is cosy (Cosy)	3.8400	2
3	This mall is very ambient (Ambient)	3.8000	3
4	This mall is located at the center of the city (Location)	3.6800	4
5	This mall is overcrowded (Over Crowded)	3.0600	5

Table no 2 shows the significance value of mean analysis. Highest mean is given to the factor atmosphere (4.60) followed by cosy is next highest mean value (3.84).

Table 3- Mean Analysis:

Analysis of mean based on the Leisure at forum mall.

S. No	Dimensions of Leisure	Mean	Rank
1	This mall is enormous when it comes to Concerts & Artistic Events (Events)	4.0200	1
2	There are high-quality cafes in this mall (Cafes)	3.8600	2
3	Restaurants(Food Court) in this mall are good	3.7800	3
4	Most of the products in this mall have a great value for money (Value)	3.6800	4
5	Shops in the mall are well stocked (Shops)	3.5400	5

Table no 3 shows the significance value of mean analysis. Highest mean is given to the factor events (4.02) followed by cafes is next highest mean value (3.86).

Table 4 - Mean Analysis:

Analysis of mean based on the Convenience in forum mall.

S. No	Dimensions of Convenience	Mean	Rank
1	The opening and closing time hours of this mall are fine (Timing)	4.0000	1
2	The restrooms are clean and easily accessible in the mall (Restrooms)	3.8600	2
3	This mall is close to my home (Home)	3.5800	3
4	Parking in this mall is easy (Parking)	3.5800	4
5	This mall is close to my college/workplace (Workplace/College)	3.3800	5

Table no 4 shows the significance value of mean analysis. Highest mean is given to the factor Mall Timing (4.00) followed by Clean restrooms is next highest mean value (3.86).

Table 5 - Mean Analysis:

Analysis of mean based on the Theatre at forum mall.

S.No	Dimensions of Theatre	Mean	Rank
1	How convenient is it to book tickets online? (Online)	4.3600	1
2	How good is your theatre experience? (Experience)	4.2200	2
3	I prefer to watch movie on weekends (Weekends)	4.0200	3
4	Ticket prices for the movie are acceptable (Price)	3.7200	4
5	I prefer to watch movie on weekdays (Weekdays)	3.5200	5

Table no 5 shows the significance value of mean analysis. Highest mean is given to the factor online booking (4.36) followed by theatre experience is next highest mean value (4.22).

Table 6- Independent sample T test:

Analysis of difference on perception based on Gender.

Null Hypothesis:

There is no significance difference between gender with respect to customer perception at forum mall.

Alternative Hypothesis:

There is a significance difference between gender with respect to customer perception at forum mall.

S.No	Customer Perception in Vijaya Mall	Gender	
		t	Sig
1	Atmosphere	0.132	0.987
2	Leisure	1.212	0.566
3	Convenience	1.267	0.284
4	Theatre	2.120	0.266

Table no 6 shows the significance value of independent sample t test. The significance value should be less than 0.05 for accepting the alternative hypothesis. In this case the majority of variables are greater than 0.05. Hence there is no significant difference between **gender** with respect to customer perception at forum mall.

Table 7- Anova analysis:

Analysis of Age and perception ,Occupation and perception and Education and perception towards Consumers in Forum Vijaya Mall

S.No	Customer perception at Vijaya Mall	Age		Occupation		Education	
		f	Sig	f	Sig	f	Sig
1	Atmosphere	0.216	0.885	1.269	0.296	0.676	0.513
2	Leisure	0.710	0.551	0.027	0.994	0.036	0.965
3	Convenience	0.083	0.969	0.567	0.640	0.525	0.595
4	Theatre	3.459	0.024	1.287	0.290	0.112	0.894

Since the significant value of age, occupation and education with respect to the customer perception of forum vijaya mall is >0.05 accepting the null hypothesis (H_0).The customer perception is equal for both gender relationship between the Shoppers is common for all significant. This table shows that there is no significant difference among the age, occupation and education with respect to the customer perception at Forum Vijaya mall.

Conclusion:

Shoppers love the shopping activity in mall due to availability of unique products across all brands under one roof. The discounts offered at malls are comparatively high rather than retail outlets. The study concluded that forum vijaya mall has been a great entertainment for working professionals and students on all days. The mall has been crowded not only on weekends but also on weekdays. Main viewpoint of the Shoppers visiting this mall are “Convenience” “Layout” “Theatre experience” “Fun-filled events on weekends” “Leisure” and “Atmosphere”.

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